

Scope & Topics

Computer-aided technologies (IJCAx) mean the use of computer technology to aid in the design, analysis and manufacture various products. International Journal of Computer-Aided technologies (IJCAx) is an open access, peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of Computer Aided technologies such as CAD, CAM, CAIM, CAR, CARD, CASE etc. The journal focuses on all technical and practical aspects of Computer Aided technologies. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on advanced CAx tools and establishing new collaborations in these areas. Authors are solicited to contribute to this journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in all Computer Aided technologies

Topics considered include but are not limited to:

- lifecycle management
- Product Data Management
- Finite Element Analysis
- CAx software tools (CAD/CAM/CAE/CAID/CARD/CARE/CASE/ PLM/ERP/DNC/CAQ)
- Data Mining
- Digital/virtual prototyping, object archival and retrieval
- Enterprise Resource Planning
- Knowledge based Engineering
- Computer Aided Manufacturing Technologies
- Computation Geometry
- Computer Graphics
- Human machine and human computer interaction
- Optimization

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: ijcax@airccse.org. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : December 01, 2018**
- **Notification** : January 01, 2019
- **Final Manuscript Due** : January 09, 2019
- **Publication Date** : **Determined by the Editor-in-Chief**

For other details please visit <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcax/index.html>